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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The aims of this research were to identify the factors affecting milk consumption of rural households. As well as to determine the effects of these factors on the rural household's intention to consume milk. A random sample of 514 rural households in northern Vietnam was selected to collect data on their milk consumption. Methodologically, statistical analysis was used to identify the preferences of rural households in purchasing dairy products and the two-step econometric technique was applied to measure the effects of the socio-economic and demographic factors and characteristics of milk market on milk consumption of the rural households. The integrating results from the two models showed that household's income and convenience in milk buying have strongly positive effects on milk consumption of the rural households. At the lighter level, numbers of children and elders in the rural household also have positive effects on the probability of milk purchasing of rural households and milk expenditure while educational level was only found to affect milk expenditure of the rural households. In contrast, age of the rural household head and the importance of milk price have significant negative effects on both decisions of milk consumption of the rural households, decision to buy milk and level of milk expenditure. Finally, several implications of this study highlighted the contribution of the research to theory by enriching body of literature and marketing perspective by showing the worthy bases for the companies to determine their target rural consumers and improve their products.

Keywords: Milk consumption, rural household, northern Vietnam

1. INTRODUCTION

There is a growing change in the food market in the world, especially in developing countries. This change is based on increasing in consumers' standards of living which are considered as the factors affecting the changing lifestyles and worldwide trends in consumption (Liu et al., 2009; Kou and Li, 2008; Rajesh and Arunabha, 2007). Therefore, understanding the requirements of different segments of the population helps enterprises and their marketers to identify the different sets of consumers and their consumption preferences (Babolian and Ab Karim, 2010).

In Vietnam, the rural area comprising over 70% of total population plays an important role in economic development (Trung, 2013). The great results of economic development in the rural area have led to more affluent consumers who demand higher quality food products. Moreover, rural consumers who are more educated are now more conscious about health and wellness issues related to food choices and diet (Phuong and Marcus, 2013). In fact, food industry has significantly transformed to meet the increasing needs and preferences of the consumers (Hoang 2009).

Regarding milk consumption, it is important to find the association between personal and environmental factors with intention to consume milk and therefore enterprises involving milk business will have helpful decisions and strategic planning for expanding their business. As the consequence, demands for dairy products are increasing dramatically as consumers in Vietnam become more affluent (Thuy and Duong, 2013). For the consumers, milk and other dairy products are the best biologically utilized source of calcium (Charles, 1992). Hence, increasing milk consumption is the best way to increase dietary calcium intake level, especially children and elders. Although per capita consumption of dairy products in Vietnam is substantially lower than the other Asian emerging economies such as Thailand and China (14.8 liters of milk per person a year in 2010 compared to 23 and 18 liters in Thailand and China, respectively), it has strongly and steadily increased in the past decades (FAOSTAT, 2011).

This paper aims to (1) identify and describe the factors affecting milk consumption of rural household, (2) examine the factors influencing milk consumption of rural households in northern Vietnam, and (3) suggest recommendations which contribute to improve the management of dairy supply chains and develop strategic plans and policies to aid in the development and expansion of the domestic dairy industry in Vietnam.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

As the corollary, rural consumers' income improved create a potential rural market for firms to expand their business (Liu and Zhang, 2007). Recent consumer research suggests that food consumption is becoming increasingly diverse and consumers are growing more concerned about the quality, safety and nutritional content of their food (Phuong et al., 2013; Thang and Popkin, 2004). There are some factors which were cited as the key driving forces within the food consumption have been and will remain: health benefits of food (Hartog et al., 2006; Grunert et al., 1996), value of food (Alden, 2007), how the food is manufactured, convenience and suitable packaging (Hoyer and MacInnis, 1997).

Regarding factors influencing consumption of dairy products, socio-economic and demographic characteristics (e.g. gender, age, income, education, presence of young children in the household, ethnicity) and level of knowledge influence Vietnamese households' expenditure for dairy products (Phuong et al., 2013a). Accordingly, the potential of increasing household's income, higher level of education and greater presence of young children in the household have positive effects on the household's consumption of dairy products. The Vietnamese households' expenditure for dairy products is also significantly different across two household groups: rural household and urban household.

Aside from the socio-economic and demographic factors discussed above, consumers' health consciousness has been found to significantly affect the household's consumption of dairy products. Bonaventure and Wendy (2012), and McGill et al. (2008) found that consumers who perceive dairy products as a good source of nutrients have higher consumption level of dairy products than other consumers. Grunert et al. (2000) suggest that manufacturers/processors and marketers must understand consumers' perceptions of dairy product quality. He added that consumers consider four dimensions when forming perceptions about dairy product quality. These includes: hedonic (e.g. sensory attributes such as taste or smell), health-related, convenience-related (e.g. distance from consumer's house to markets or shops), and process-related (e.g. production processes such as organic, animal welfare).

Several studies have found that gender and presence of young children in the household significantly influence decisions on milk purchases. Female-headed households were found to be significant in affecting dairy products' expenditure (Phuong et al., 2013a). They were also generally more health-conscious than men (Radam et al., 2010). Additionally, the households with greater presence of young children less than 12 years of age were generally less concerned about price and more interested in purchasing safe milk products.

In addition to gender, ethnic group, household composition and size of young children in the household, other demographic variables such as income and educational level have been found to significantly influence milk consumption. De Alwis et al. (2009) found that the household's monthly income and level of education play a more important role in milk consumption. Consumers with higher income were more likely to purchase milk products and respondents who had completed higher level of education were more likely to consume dairy products (Ebru and Neslihan, 2013).

Also, consumers' behavior, preferences and attitudes toward consumption of dairy products substantially differs between rural and urban. By determining the effect of personal and environmental factors on children's intention to consume milk in Selangor (Malaysia), Babolian and Ab Karim (2010) showed that attitudes toward sensory properties had the highest effect while in the urban area the highest effect belongs to the availability of milk at home. Phuong et al. (2013a) found that urban households consume much more dairy products than those in rural area.

The above literature summarizes the key factors affecting the consumption behavior of households on dairy products. This research aims to add to this available literature by analyzing the factors affecting milk consumption of rural household in Northern Vietnam. To achieve the purposes of this research, variables on environmental and personal factors were applied.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Analytical Framework

The analytical framework of the research for examining the influences of the personal and environmental factors on milk consumption of rural households was proposed based on literature review (Figure 1). Among the key factors considered that may affect the milk consumption of rural households, the analysis identified two critical groups of factors. The first group comprised characteristics of individual rural households (e.g. household income, presence of young children and elders, main source of income, education, gender and age of household heads). The second group included environmental factors such as characteristics of milk market (e.g. purchasing convenience, price and purchasing safe products).

Figure 1: Analytical framework of the research.

Source: Diagram developed by the authors

3.2. Empirical models

Statistical analysis was used to identify the preference of rural households in purchasing dairy products. In addition, a two-step econometric model is used to estimate factors affecting milk consumption of rural households in northern Vietnam. To measure the effects of personal and environmental factors on milk consumption of rural households, the Heckman two-step method for estimating two related milk consumption decisions on whether or not to purchase milk and milk consumption expenditure was used. In the first step, a probit model was employed to measure the influences of factors including the individual characteristics of rural household (H) and the characteristics of milk market (M) on the decisions to purchase milk. In the second step, an OLS regression as a conditional truncated sub-model was conducted to examine the factors affecting milk consumption expenditure of rural households.

The probit technique allows an examination of the effects of a number of variables on the underlying probability of a dichotomous dependent variable. This econometric tool is useful for binary responses (yes, no) to the milk consumption of rural households. In this case, the model helps predict the likelihood that a rural household will purchase milk, given a set of related factors. The dependent variable takes a value of unity if the rural household purchases milk and zero, otherwise. The probability that a rural household will purchase milk was expressed as follows:

$$p_i = f(H_{ij}, M_{ik}) = \frac{e^{f(H_{ij}, M_{ik})}}{1 + e^{f(H_{ij}, M_{ik})}} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\alpha + \sum_j \beta_j H_{ij} + \sum_k \gamma_k M_{ik})}} \quad (1)$$

The probit model is estimated by using the maximum likelihood procedure. Where β and γ are the estimated vectors of explanatory variables, H_{ij} and M_{ik} , respectively, on the probability of making decision to purchase milk (p_i). Using

the estimates of the probit model, the probability that a rural household will purchase milk can be derived (Eq.2) by transforming Eq.1 into a linear expression which is amenable to regression method.

$$p_i^* = \alpha + \sum_j \beta_j H_{ij} + \sum_k \gamma_k M_{ik} + \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where p_i^* measures the probability of the rural household in purchasing milk.

Regarding milk consumption expenditure, the dependent variable in the estimated model was referred as the amount of money that a rural household spends for milk consumption. In the case that the rural household does not purchase milk, milk consumption was recorded as zero. Given a set of factors for both characteristics of the rural household (H) and characteristics of the milk market (M), the milk consumption expenditure for household i was hypothesized as below:

$$y_i = \prod_j H_{ij}^{\beta_j} \prod_k M_{ik}^{\gamma_k} e^{\omega_i} \quad (3)$$

Taking logarithms of both sides of Eq.3, the level of investment sub-model was restructured as follows:

$$y_i^* = \sum_j \beta_j \ln H_{ij} + \sum_k \gamma_k \ln M_{ik} + \omega_i \quad (4)$$

where y_i^* measures the logarithms of amount of money for milk consumption of the rural household i^{th} as a function of vectors of independent variables, H_{ij} and M_{ik} , and unobservable factors.

If the error terms in these two models (ε_i and ω_i) are uncorrelated, the milk consumption expenditure model can be estimated by Ordinary Least Squares (OLS). On the other hand, Heckman two-stage method is based on the assumption that a series of variables can influence rural household's decisions to purchase milk and another series of them can influence the milk consumption expenditure of the rural households. In this case, the Inverse Mills Ratio is used as an additional regressor in the milk consumption expenditure model which is only run for the rural households that decide to purchase milk. If the simple t-test suggests that the Inverse Mills Ratio is not significantly different from zero, OLS regression can be used.

3.3. Data collection

Data for the empirical analysis was obtained from the rural household consumption survey. The data was collected through direct interview of 514 individual households located in three representative provinces (Hanoi, Thai Binh and Hai Duong) in northern Vietnam. The sample was explicitly stratified by proportion of rural household income (see Table 1). The survey was conducted from July to September 2012. A structured questionnaire was designed with four sections: personal factors, socio-demographic information of the respondents, household's decisions to consume milk and environmental factors related to the characteristics of milk market. Additional information related to the research problem was also collected from various agricultural institutions, government offices, and local municipalities.

Table 1: Sample Statistics of Rural Household Consumption Survey

Type of household	Total	Representative provinces		
		Hanoi	Thai Binh	Hai Duong
High income level	121	41	26	54
Medium income level	341	92	84	165
Low income level	52	13	18	21
Total	514	146	128	240

Source: Summarize from survey data, 2012

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Identifying the most preferred criterion of rural households in purchasing milk

To understand the milk preference of households in northern Vietnam, respondents were asked to identify their most preferred criteria in purchasing milk. Even 82% of the households mentioned that quality is a factor in milk purchasing, the criterion to be evaluated as the most important is the price of milk as responded by 25.6% of the households (see Figure 2). This implies that the elasticity of price to milk consumption of rural households is high and partly shows that the rural households in northern Vietnam generally have low income. Price was closely followed by convenience in purchasing milk which was cited as the most preferred criteria in purchasing milk by 22.1% of the households surveyed. The proportions of origin, brand and quality of milk are 21.7%, 12.8% and 9.6%, respectively.

Respondents also indicated how they get information about the products and agreed or disagreed with several statements revealing their perceptions on fluid milk. Considering the proportion of rural households cited for each information source (Figure 3), it appeared that consumers generally agreed (50.8% of the households) that media is the most popular medium in understanding the characteristics of product such as price, quality, and nutritional contents (i.e. calcium and vitamins) when purchasing milk. The advice of friends (24.9%) and the salesperson's consultancy (22.2%) were also important sources of product information for the rural household to decide to buy milk.

Figure 2: Preferred criteria in purchasing milk of rural household in northern Vietnam.

Source: Drawn from survey data, 2012

One of the most important issues was that marketers need to expand their business in areas where the rural households often buy milk. The proportion of respondents indicated in Figure 3 show where they usually buy milk. Over 55% of the surveyed households indicated that they often buy milk in retail shops and roughly a quarter of them (28.2%) frequently choose local markets in buying milk. Meanwhile, only 16.2% of the households often purchase milk in supermarkets and about 3.4% of the respondents mainly buy milk from hawkers.

Figure 3: Sources of information about products and where rural households in northern Vietnam buy their milk.

Source: Drawn from survey data, 2012

4.2. Identification and description of variables

Based on the review of literature (Section 2) and the criteria identified by the rural households as the most preferred in purchasing milk (Sub-section 4.1), explanatory variables assumed to have effects on milk consumption of rural households are outlined in Table 2. Accordingly, major characteristics of the surveyed households and factors of milk market were expressed. To explore the effects of the personal and environmental factors on milk consumption of rural households, they were both included in models of binary choice decision of milk purchasing and expenditure of milk consumption as categorical variables.

Table 2: Definition and statistical description of the variables used in empirical models

Variables	Definition	Mean		
		All sample (n=514)	Buying milk group (n=454)	Not buying milk group (n=60)
Dependent variables				
Milk_choice	Dummy (=1) if rural household decides to buy milk and (=0), otherwise.	0.9040		
Milk_exp	Amount of money for milk consumption of rural household per month (million VND)	0.8382		
Explanatory variables				
Income	Income level of rural household per month (thousand VND)	9.5859	9.8591	7.0133
Children	Number of children less than 6 year olds in rural household (person)	0.8896	0.9752	0.0833
Elders	Number of elders more than 60 year old in rural household (person)	0.1584	0.1752	0.0000
Age	Age of person who holds power to make decision of milk consumption in rural household (year)	37.968	37.574	41.683
Education	Number of school-years of person who holds power to make decision of milk consumption in rural household (year)	9.7120	9.7894	8.9833
Gender	Dummy (=1) if the person who holds power to make decision of milk consumption in rural household is female and (=0), others.	0.7440	0.7381	0.8000
Convenience	Dummy (=1) if the respondent's assessment on place to buy milk is convenient and (=0), otherwise.	0.8624	0.9504	0.0333
Price_percep	Dummy (=1) if person who holds power to make decision of milk purchasing considers price as the most important criteria and (=0), otherwise.	0.7872	0.8106	0.3333
Hou_char	Dummy (=1) if rural household does farming and (=0), otherwise.	0.6760	0.7018	0.4333
Origin	Dummy (=1) if person who holds power of making decision to buy imported milk as the most preferred and (=0), otherwise.	0.5593	0.5872	0.4833

Source: Calculated from survey data, 2012

Data shown in Table 2 also provides the summary statistics of dependent variables in the models. The 90.4% of all rural households in the sample decided to buy milk with the average expenditure of over 838 thousand VND per month. Moreover, the statistics indicated the mean of a wide set of explanatory variables for both individual characteristics of rural households and factors of milk market. The three main characteristics of rural households include income level, presence of children and number of elders. The average income level was 9.586 million VND while the average number of children and elders were 0.89 and 0.16, respectively. The average age and educational level of the person who hold power to decide the household's milk consumption in the rural household were 37.9 years and 9.71 school years, respectively.

The source of income of the majority of rural households (67.6% of the sample) was from farming activities. About 74.4% of the persons who hold power to make decisions of milk consumption were female while over 72.8% of them consider price as the most important criterion in milk consumption. Differences exist in terms of the factors related to milk market as well. For example, up to 86.24% of the respondents cited that a convenient place to buy milk has an important effect on their milk consumption while 55.93% of the respondents prefer imported milk brands than domestic products.

4.3. Measuring the factors affecting decision to buy milk

The estimated results from the binary choice in the probit model of milk consumption decision are presented in Table 3. This shows the estimated coefficients and the goodness of fit for the model. The likelihood ratio statistic (LR) suggested that the whole estimated regression model is significant at 1% level ($p < 0.01$). Therefore, this model is reliable for the future analysis. The main hypothesis under examination is whether the presence of the personal and environmental factors significantly affects the probability in making decisions when buying milk. Most of the explanatory variables have significant effect on the rural household's decision, except for the occupational characteristics of rural household, milk traceability, educational level and gender of the head of rural household.

The results showed that individual characteristics of rural household such as income and number of children in the rural household are significant factors ($p < 0.05$) affecting the rural household's decision to buy milk. Accordingly, if the rural household has one more children will lead to increase in the probability of milk consumption by over 0.04 percent while one more million VND increase in income's rural household will also cause increase the probability of milk consumption by near 0.16 percent. Meanwhile, if the rural household has one more elder as its member, the probability of milk consumption will increase by almost 0.053 percent at 10% significant level. These effects are positive which mean that higher income levels of the rural households can translate to more ability to buy milk to satisfy consumption needs. Children and the elders are being prioritized when it comes to milk consumption in the households.

Among the personal characteristics that affect the milk purchasing decision of the rural households, the effect of age was negative. As age of the head of rural household increases by one year, the probability of milk consumption will decrease by almost 0.4 percent, *ceteris paribus*. Normally, young couples have to take more care of their children compared to the older heads, thereby reducing the probability of milk purchasing for older rural households heads. Similarly, the perception of the rural household heads on milk price was also negative with the probability of their milk purchasing decision. If the head of the rural household considers the price of milk as the most important criterion for making the decision to buy milk, then, it implied that the budget for milk consumption of the rural household was limited and in this case the probability of milk consumption was reduced by over 0.4 percent.

Table 3: Results of the probit model of the decision to buy milk

Variables	Coefficient		Z values	P> z
Constant	-.28409	NS	-0.27	0.785
Income	.15651	*	1.83	0.067
Children	.04123	***	2.58	0.009
Elders	.05280	**	2.29	0.021
Age	-.39235	**	-2.38	0.017
Education	.11195	NS	0.84	0.397
Gender	-.01301	NS	-0.78	0.432
Convenience	.61890	***	9.25	0.000
Hou_char	-.00261	NS	-0.16	0.871
Price_percep	-.04075	***	-2.63	0.008
Milk_origin	.00914	NS	0.61	0.537
Pseudo R2	0.6823			
LR chi2(9)	274.17	***		
Number of obs	514			

Notes: *, **, *** are significant levels at 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively.

4.4. Estimating the factors affecting milk consumption expenditure of rural households

To test the sample selection bias, the model of milk consumption expenditure was first estimated using the Heckman two-stage procedure. All the variables assumed to affect the milk consumption expenditure of rural households were included in the model and most of them were found to be significant in the model. Results from the non-nested test indicated that the model can be re-estimated using OLS regression. Linear regression model was estimated in the forms of logarithmic function. Independent variables used in the linear regression model include characteristics of rural households (i.e., income level, number of children and elders in the rural households, main income source), personal characteristics of the rural household head (i.e., age, educational level, gender, perception of milk price and quality/safety) and characteristics of milk market (i.e., convenience to buy milk).

As shown in Table 4, the estimated results revealed that the 63.5% changes in mean amount of money of the rural households can be explained by the independent variables in the model. The statistic F is 106.81 and the probability value showed total significance of fitted regression at 1% level. The considered model is therefore reliable for analysis of the next results.

Table 4: Results of the OLS model of milk expenditure

Variables	Coefficient		t values	P> t
Constant	0.79278	***	7.09	0.000
Income	.26013	***	5.28	0.000
Children	.10399	***	4.89	0.000
Elders	.10891	***	3.56	0.000
Age	-.24069	**	-2.47	0.014
Education	.19393	**	2.24	0.026
Gender	-.02242	NS	-1.01	0.311
Convenience	.17181	***	23.32	0.000
Hou_char	.03131	NS	1.46	0.146
Price_percep	-.06709	***	-3.26	0.001
Milk_origin	-.02072	NS	-1.05	0.295
R-squared	0.6350			
F(10,503)	106.81	***		
Number of obs	514			

Notes: *, **, *** significant at 10%, 5% and 1% levels, respectively.

The positive significant estimated coefficient for income variable indicated that, on the average, if the rural household's income increases by one million VND per month, it will cause an over 0.26 million VND per month increase in milk expenditure, holding all other things in constant. This implies that the rural households who have higher income levels will buy more milk to satisfy their consumption needs. Thus, as the standard of living of the rural population is improving, the marketers should take the opportunity to expand their business operation. Similarly, the effects of presence of children and elders in the rural households were positively significant at 1% level on expenditure of milk consumption. As discussed above, children and elders were prioritized persons for milk consumption because of the need to take care of their health. Since milk is a highly nutritious food, they consider milk consumption as necessary.

Regarding the personal characteristics of the rural household head, the age of the household head had negative effect on the mean expenditure of milk consumption of rural households. It suggests that a one year increase in age of the household head will lead to a decrease in the mean expenditure of milk consumption of rural household in one month by 0.24 million VND, *ceteris paribus*. Normally, the old heads have mature children and their parents may have died already, therefore they spend less money for milk consumption than the younger heads.

Similarly, if the rural household head considered milk prices as the most important criterion in purchasing milk, the mean expenditure of milk consumption of rural household in one month will decrease by nearly 0.07 million VND. This implies that the household heads obtaining higher levels of education often have better jobs and therefore, have more money to buy milk. Meanwhile, the rural household heads consider milk price as a prerequisite in buying milk. This is because of their low income which equates to less money for buying milk. In contrast, the estimated coefficient of education variable is 0.19. If all factors remain constant, a one unit increase in educational level rural household head will lead to 0.19 million VND increase in their milk consumption. The rural household heads with higher educational levels generally know better how to earn money. They are also regarded as persons with higher perception of nutrition.

Finally, the estimated coefficient of milk market environment showed that if the respondent consider the place for buying milk as convenient, then, the mean expenditure of milk consumption of rural household in one month will increase by 0.17 million VND. This indicator suggests that establishing sales network through developing systems retail stores or stalls in rural markets is crucial for firms that are expanding their business in rural areas. This is because majority of rural people still prefer to buy milk in local markets or small shops near their house than in the supermarket away from their house.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

The paper identified the personal and environmental factors which were considered influence on milk purchasing decisions of rural households such as whether to buy or not to buy milk and the budget for purchasing. They are household income, main income source of the household, presence of children and elders in rural household, age, gender and educational level of the rural household head, head's perception on milk price and origin, and convenience of the place for buying milk. The impacts of these factors on milk consumption of rural households in northern Vietnam were examined by using a two-step econometric technique.

The integrating results from the two models showed that household's income and convenience in milk buying have strongly positive effects on milk consumption of the rural households. The estimated coefficients of these factors on the probability of decision to consume milk in the rural area were 0.16% and 0.62%, respectively. At the lighter level, numbers of children and elders in the rural household also have positive effects on the probability of milk purchasing of rural households and milk expenditure. Their effects on the probability of decision to consume milk for the rural households were showed by the estimated coefficients which range from 0.04% to 0.06%. Meanwhile, educational level was only found to affect milk expenditure of the rural households with the estimated coefficient approximately 0.194. In contrast, age of the rural household head and the importance of milk price have significant negative effects on both decisions of milk consumption of the rural households, decision to buy milk and level of milk expenditure. Accordingly, the probability of the rural household making decision to buy milk decrease by over 0.39% and near 0.41% if the rural household head adds an age and considers milk price as the most important criterion in buying milk, respectively.

There are several implications of this study. In terms of theoretical contributions, the research enriched the body of literature of rural household's intention to consume milk. The findings of this research could provide a foundation for future research in this topic and contribute significantly to develop better understanding on the milk consumption of rural household among Vietnam. The results of this research showed that convenience in buying milk had the highest effect among other factors on the probability of milk purchasing of rural households, while, in terms of milk expenditure of the rural households the highest effect belongs to household's income. From the marketing perspective, the findings of this study could assist companies to understand better the rural consumers' preferences and characteristics of milk market in the rural area. Accordingly, the factors such as milk price, nutritional quality of milk and convenience in milk buying were considered as worthy bases for the companies to determine their target consumers in the rural area. Besides that, the results of this research would be useful to processors and producers involving milk to further improve their products and to be more competitive in the market.

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REFERENCES

- Alden, D.L., Steenkamp, J.B.E.M. and Batra, R. (2007), *Consumer attitudes toward market place globalization: Structure, antecedents and consequences*, International Journal of Research Marketing 23: 227-239.
- Babolian H.R. and Ab Karim M.S. (2010), *Factors affecting milk consumption among school children in urban and rural areas of Selangor, Malaysia*, International Food Research Journal 17: 651-660.
- Bonaventure Boniface1 and Wendy J. Umberger (2012), *Factors influencing Malaysian consumers' consumption of dairy products*, Paper for presentation at the 56th AARES annual conference, Fremantle, Western Australia, February 7-10, 2012.

- Charles, P. (1992), *Calcium absorption and calcium bioavailability*, Journal of Internal Medicine 231: 161-168.
- De Alwis A.E.N, J.C. Edirisinghe and A.M.T.P. Athauda (2009), *Analysis of Factors Affecting Fresh Milk Consumption among the Mid-Country Consumers*, Tropical Agricultural Research & Extension 12(2): 2009 pp.103-109.
- Ebru O. and Neslihan Y. (2013), *The factors affecting milk consumption preferences of the consumers Edirne Keşan township sample*, Journal: Food, Agriculture and Environment, Vol. 11, Issue 3&4, pp.516-518.
- FAOSTAT (2011), *Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations: Statistical Databases*, Retrieved from <http://www.devtest.fao.org/cgi-bin/nph-db.pl>, Available on December 11, 2013.
- Grunert, K.G., Hartvig Larsen, H., Madsen, T.K. and Baadsgaard, A. (1996), *Market orientation in food and agriculture*, Boston: Kluwer Aca Publisher.
- Grunert, K.G., TinoBech-Larsen, and Bredahl, L. (2000), *Three issues in consumer quality perception and acceptance of dairy products*, International Dairy Journal (10): 575-584.
- Hartog, A.P., Staveren, W.A.V. and Brouwer, I.D. (2006), *Food habits and consumption in developing countries: Manual for field studies*, Netherland: Wageningen publishing.
- Hoang Vu Linh (2009), *Estimation of Food Demand from Household Survey Data in Vietnam*, DEPOCEN Working Paper - Series No. 2009/12, Center for Agricultural Policy, Institute of Policy and Strategy for Agriculture and Rural.
- Hoyer, W.D. and MacInnis, D.J. (1997), *Consumer behavior*, Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Kou M. and Li L. (2008), *Distribution of expenditure of rural consumers and analysis of consumption level in China*, Rural economy/2008 (5): 74-78.
- Liu C. and Zhang Y. (2007), *The constraints of and Countermeasures on the expansion of the consumption of Chinese peasants*, Journal of US-China Administration ISSN1548-6591, Vol.4, No.1, (Serial No.26), USA.
- Liu M., Wang G. and Wang H. (2009), *Propensity analysis on consumption expenditure of rural residents in Hebei province - China*, Asian Agricultural Research/2009, 1 (8): 20-23, 43.
- McGill, C. R., Fulgoni, V. L., DiRienzo, D., Huth, P. J., Kurilich, A. C., and Miller, G. D. (2008), *Contribution of dairy products to dietary potassium intake in the United States Population*, Journal of the American College of Nutrition, 27(1), 44-50.
- Phuong H. Nguyen, Garrett Strizich, Alyssa Lowe, Hieu Nguyen, Hoa Pham, Truong V. Truong, Son Nguyen, Reynaldo Martorell and Usha Ramakrishnan (2013), *Food consumption patterns and associated factors among Vietnamese women of reproductive age*, Nutrition Journal 2013, 12:126.
- Phuong, N.V. & Marcus M. (2013), *Meat consumption patterns in Vietnam: Effects of household characteristics on pork and poultry consumption*, Poster presentation at the 53rd Annual Conference of the German Society of Economic and Social Sciences in Agriculture (GEWISOLA): How much market and how much regulation does sustainable agricultural development need?, Berlin, September 25-27, 2013.
- Phuong V. Nguyen, M. Mergenthaler and Cuong H. Tran (2013a), *Effects of socio-economic and demographic variables on Vietnamese households' expenditure for dairy products*, Paper for presentation at the Tropentag Symposium: Agricultural development within the rural-urban continuum, Stuttgart-Hohenheim, Stuttgart, Germany, September 17-19, 2013.
- Radam, A., M.R. Yacob, T. Siew Bee, and J. Selamat. (2010), *Consumers' perceptions, attitudes and willingness to pay towards food products with "No Added Msg" labeling*, International Journal of Marketing Studies 2 (1): 65-77.
- Rajesh, K. A. and Arunabha, M. (2007), *Rural telecom in India: Marketing issues and experiences from other countries*, Paper presented at ICEG conference, Dec 2007, Retrieved from <http://www.csi-sigegov.org/3/323193.pdf>, Available on December 11, 2013.
- Thang, N. M. and B. M. Popkin (2004), *Patterns of food consumption in Vietnam: Effects on socioeconomic groups during an era of economic growth*, European Journal of Clinical Nutrition, 58(1):145-53.
- Thuy D. T. T. and Duong L. T. B. (2013), *Vietnam dairy market: The milky opportunities*, Paper for the Kantar Worldpanel Dairy Talk on May 8th, 2013, Ho Chi Minh city, Vietnam.
- Trung Q. Tran (2013), *Rural investment climate and business activities of agro-enterprise: Evidence from Northern area of Vietnam*, PhD dissertation in Accounting, Graduate School, Tokyo University of Agriculture, Japan.